

ISic0437

Epitaph for Ofillia Proba and L. Ofillius Faustus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Napoli

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Of]illia · Proba

2. sibi · et · L(ucio) · Ofillio

3. Fausto · patrono

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

Ofillia Proba (made this) for herself and her patron Lucius Ofillius Faustus

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 536801

EDCS 11501745

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae*

Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 10.7157 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650769>)

Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 683

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